

**HR POLICY AND RECRUITMENT PROCESS IN QnQ HEALTHCARE
PVT LTD, CHENNAI**

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Cite This Article: N. Kiran & Dr. B. Velmurugan, "HR Policy and Recruitment Process in QnQ Healthcare Pvt Ltd, Chennai", Indo American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Review, Volume 8, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 41-47, 2024.

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Abstract:

Recruitment is the process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating them to apply for jobs in the organization. Selection may be defined as the process by which the organization chooses from among the applicants, those people whom they feel would best meet the job requirement, considering current environmental condition. In today's rapidly changing business environment, organizations have to respond quickly to requirements for people. Hence, it is important to have a well-defined recruitment policy in place, which can be executed effectively to get the best fits for the vacant positions. Selecting the wrong candidate or rejecting the right candidate could turn out to be costly mistakes for the organization.

Key Words: Recruitment, Selection, Reference, Interview, Hiring, Performance.

Introduction:

A HR policy is a formalized human resources document that presents a broad overview of standard operating policies and procedures for an organization. It is an essential document that provides structure and establishes consistency and discipline in decision-making and employee behaviour. HR policy is a booklet or a piece of document that gives the reader a fair idea of the working procedures of the particular company or organization. They give guidelines on how to apply the rules and regulations that a company has set for its functioning. This kind of policy is especially useful for HR officials so that they do not break rules that may lead the company to societal and legal problems. Thus, it is quite evident that an HR policy is of some importance to organizations for smooth functioning. They also need to be reviewed and revised time and again so that the management of the company keeps up with the changing trends and also keep track of new legal acts that may be enforced upon the working of organizations.

HR Policies - Introduction:

A policy is a guide for repetitive action in major areas of business. It is a statement of commonly accepted understanding of decision-making criteria. Policies are set up to achieve several benefits. By taking policy decisions on frequently recurring problems, the top management provides the guidelines to lower level managers. Efficient utilization of resources depends a great deal upon:

- The efficiency of personnel operating and handling the resources,
- The image of the management in the minds of employees, and
- The relations between the management and the workers.

Strategic Human Resource Planning:

Human resource planning is a process that identifies current and future human resources needs for an organization to achieve its goals. Human resource planning should serve as a link between human resource management and the overall strategic plan of an organization. Ageing workers population in most western countries and growing demands for qualified workers in developing economies have underscored the importance of effective human resource planning. This Strategic HR Planning and evaluation cycle is depicted in the diagram to the right. Human resource planning is the on-going process of systematic planning to achieve the best use of an organization's most valuable asset – its human resources.

Implementation Stages:

Assessing the Current HR Capacity:

Develop a skills catalogue for your employees so that you have a clear understanding of what your staffs currently hold. This employee catalogue should include everything from volunteer activities to certifications, of all degrees not just topics pertaining to their particular position. These catalogues can be assessed to deem whether or not an employee is ready to add more responsibility, or to forecast the employee's future development plans.

Forecasting HR Requirements:

This step includes projecting what the HR needs for the future will be based on the strategic goals of the organization. Keep in mind you will need to also accommodate for external challenges that can affect your organization.

Gap Analysis:

During this step you will observe where your organization is currently, and where you want to be in the future. You will identify things such as, the employee count, and the skills evaluation and compare it to what will be needed to achieve your future goal. During this phase you should also review your current HR practices and identify what you are doing that is useful and what you can add, that will help you achieve your goal.

Developing HR Strategies to Support the Strategies of the Organization:

The HR strategies that you can follow to meet your organizational goals.

Restructuring Strategies:

This includes reducing staff, regrouping tasks to create well-designed jobs, and reorganizing work groups to perform more efficiently.

Training and Development Strategies:

This includes providing the current staff with training and development opportunities to encompass new roles in the organization

Recruitment Strategies:

This includes recruiting new hires that already have the skills the organization will need in the future.

Outsourcing Strategies:

This includes outreaching to external individuals or organizations to complete certain tasks.

Collaboration Strategies:

This includes collaborating with other organizations to learn from how others do things, allow employees to gain skills and knowledge not previously available in their own organization. Human resource policies are continuing guidelines on the approach an organization intends to adopt in managing its people. They represent specific guidelines to HR managers on various matters concerning employment and state the intent of the organization on different aspects of Human Resource management such as recruitment, promotion, compensation, training, selections etc. They therefore serve as a reference point when human resources management practices are being developed or when decisions are being made about an organization's workforce. A good HR policy provides generalized guidance on the approach adopted by the organization, and therefore its employees, concerning various aspects of employment. A procedure spells out precisely what action should be taken in line with the policies.

Each organization has a different set of circumstances and so develops an individual set of human resource policies. The locations an organization operates in will also dictate the content of their policies. Human resource policies are the formal rules and guidelines that businesses put in place to hire, train, assess, and reward the members of their workforce. These policies, when organized and disseminated in an easily used form, can serve to preempt many misunderstandings between employees and employers about their rights and obligations in the business place. It is tempting, as a new medium business owner, to focus on the concerns of the business at hand, and put off the task of writing up a human resource policy. All business analysts and employment lawyers will advise a new business owner to get a policy down on paper, even if it is a simple one drafted from a boilerplate model. Having policies written is important so that it is clear to all what the policies are and that they are applied consistently and fairly across the organization. Moreover, when issues concerning employee rights and company policies come before federal and state courts, it is standard practice to assume that the company's human resource policies, whether written or verbal, are a part of an employment contract between the employee and the company. Without clearly written policies, the company is at a disadvantage.

Medium businesses and especially business start-ups cannot afford to fritter away valuable time and resources on drawn-out policy disputes or potentially expensive lawsuits. Having a human resource policy in place from the start can help to avoid this situation. The business owner who takes the time to establish sound, comprehensive human resource policies will be far better equipped to succeed over the long run than the business owner who deals with each policy decision as it erupts. The latter ad hoc style is much more likely to produce inconsistent, uninformed, and legally questionable decisions that may cripple an otherwise prosperous business. For as many medium business consultants state, human resource policies that are inconsistently applied or based on faulty or incomplete data will almost inevitably result in declines in worker morale, deterioration in employee loyalty, and increased vulnerability to legal penalties. To help ensure that personnel management policies are applied fairly, business owners and consultants alike recommend that medium business enterprises produce and maintain a written record of its HR policies and of instances in which those policies came into play.

Company HR Policies:

Medium business owners should make sure that they address the following basic human resource issues when putting together their personnel policies:

- Recruitment and Selection Process
- Induction Program
- Workdays, paydays, and pay advances

- Overtime compensation
- Meal periods and break periods
- Payroll deductions
- Vacation policies
- Holidays
- Casual Leaves
- Performance Appraisal
- Termination policies
- Accommodation for Employees
- Welfare activities

Templates that may be used to create a first human resource policy document are available from many sources. Two such sources that are reputable and offer information of a full range of employment issues are the National Human Resource Association and the Society for Human Resource Managers. Each maintains a Web site with information on the services it provides and pointers to other reputable service providers.

A broad spectrum of issues can be addressed in human resource policies, depending on the nature of the business in question. Examples of such issues include promotion policies; medical/dental benefits provided to employees; use of company equipment / resources (access to Internet, personal use of fax machines and telephones, etc.); continuity of policies; sexual harassment; substance abuse and/or drug testing; smoking; flextime and telecommuting policies; pension, profit-sharing, and retirement plans; reimbursement of employee expenses (for travelling expenses and other expenses associated with conducting company business); child or elder care; educational assistance; grievance procedures; employee privacy; dress codes; parking; mail and shipping; and sponsorship of recreational activities.

Policies & Regulations:

Human Resources policies and procedures establish a framework and set standards that guide how we should conduct ourselves as employees and members of the broader Princeton community. This includes how we perform our jobs, make decisions, interact with one another and manage the business operations of the University. Refer to the Introduction to HR Policy & Procedure Manual in the Introduction Section below. In addition to this site for HR policies, the University Policy website serves as a resource for the University community as a central repository of University policies that govern a wide range of University activities. HR staff members play a vital role to help managers and staff interpret and apply our policies equitably and fairly. Please contact HR for assistance. In addition, all employees share responsibility for protecting the well-being of the community and for adhering to norms of behavior that make this a great place to work. For more information about rights and responsibilities of employees and applicable regulations, e.g., Title IX, Equal Opportunity, please visit our Rights & Responsibilities Web page. All employees are expected to be familiar with Rights, Rules, Responsibilities, a fundamental guide for all members of the Princeton University community, containing University principles of general conduct and regulations. Included on this website in section 10 below are all employer notices and/or posters required by the federal and state government

Statement of Problem:

The main assumption is that most of the organization needs policies to ensure consistency in action and equity in its relation with employees and employer. Policies perform the purpose of achieving organizational goals in a correct and effective manner. HR policies compose the basis for sound HRM practices. HR policies serve as a standard procedure for the manager. Human Resources Policies and Procedures are important as they provide structure, control, consistency, fairness and reasonableness in electrical industry. They also make ensure compliance with employment legislation and should be informed to employees of their responsibilities and the Company's expectations. The presence of HR policy is so important. If your organization does not direct absence, then there is likely to be a high cost in operational and financial terms. It is essential that managers introduce an efficient absence management system to drive down absenteeism, and prevent it as much as possible. HR policy is about reducing employee absenteeism usually happens due to illness or injury through policies and procedures.

Objective of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- To study the amendments made in the HR Policies and recruitment process of QnQ Healthcare (P) Limited, Chennai the time of incorporation.

Secondary Objectives:

- To Study the amendments in the base policy and prepare a final policy.
- To Examine a HR Policy manual for the QnQ Healthcare (P) Limited, Chennai with special emphasis on the "Managerial Service Conditions"
- To understand the HR policies maintaining the sound relation among Employees & Employer.
- To find out the employees' satisfaction towards satisfied with the implementation of policy in organization.

Need of the Study:

The researcher has considered the study necessary because organisational HR Policy can be said to be directly related with the performance of the workers in the organisation. Individuals have certain expectations and fulfillment of these expectations depends upon their perception as to how the organizational climate suits to the satisfaction of their needs. Thus organizational climate provides a type of work environment in which individuals feel satisfied or dissatisfied. In order to understand the real impact of organizational climate in the organisation the researcher has undergone the study.

Scope of the Study:

- The human resource practice is very important to practice HR policy implementation in an organisation. It is necessary for every organisation to study HR policy and know the HR policies of the company.
- It is a study on the attitude on the employees to their jobs and the reasons for the employees to change the organisation periodically. However, for the main aim of meaningful and convenient accomplishment of this study
- It has been given in respect that how effective HR policy implementation yields employee development, employee relations, employee voice, employment, equal opportunity, grievances, health and safety, managing diversity, promotion, employee performance, employee welfare , and high performance in an organization.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Hypothesis:

A hypothesis is an assumption that is made based on some evidence. This is the initial point of any investigation that translates the research questions into prediction. It includes components like variables, population and the relation between the variables. A research hypothesis that is used to test the relationship between two or more variables.

Characteristics of Hypothesis:

Following are the characteristics of hypothesis

- The hypothesis should be clear and precise to consider it to be reliable
- If the hypothesis is a relational hypothesis then it should be stating the relationship Between variables
- The hypothesis must be specific and should have scope for conducting more tests
- The way of explanation of the hypothesis must be very simple and it should be understood that the simplicity of the hypothesis is not related to its significance.

Sources of Hypothesis:

Following are the sources of hypothesis:

- The resemblance between the phenomenon
- Observation from past studies present day experience and from the competitors
- Scientific theories

Research Design:

A sample is a subset from the total population. A sample is a subset from the total population. It refers to the techniques or the procedure to the research would adopt in selecting items for the sample (i.e) the size of the sample.

Research Methodology:

The Researcher has chosen the questionnaire methods of data collection due to limited time in hand. While the designing data-collection procedure, adequate safeguards against bias and unreliability must be ensured. Researcher has examined the collected data for completeness, comprehensibility, consistently and reliability. Researcher has also gathered secondary data which have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. He got various information from journals, historical documents, magazines and report prepared by the other researchers. For the present piece of research the investor has used the following methods:

- Questionnaire
- Interview
- Observation.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

Descriptive research was undertaken to the study of the problem. The study is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research is those which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual of a group. The descriptive research describes the demographic the characteristic of the respondents and is typical concern with determining frequency with something occur show the variables vary together.

Statistical Tools:

- Simple percentage method
- Correlation
- Chi – square

Data Analysis and Interpretation:
Process of Recruitment:

Involved in Selecting a Candidate:

Comfortable with Interviewer while Interviewed:

Internal Hiring Motivates the Respondents:

Respondents view on Appreciating Their Job Role:

Findings:

- Majority 55.5 % of the Respondents are Female.
- Majority of 45.4 % of the respondents are aged between 26 – 35 Years.
- Equality 50 % of the Respondents are Married and Unmarried.
- Majority of 22.7 % of the Respondents Are UG level.
- Majority of 86.3 % of the Respondents are Permanent.
- Majority of 67.3 % of the Respondents are Other Department.
- Majority of 68.2 % of the Respondents Experience are between 0 – 5 years.
- Majority of 23.6 % of the Respondents are Strongly Agree with the HR Policy.
- Majority of 40.9 % of the Respondents are Agree with the Satisfaction of Resume Screening and Shortlisting.
- Majority of 40.9 % of the Respondents Are Agree with the Selection Policy
- Majority of 50 % of the Respondents are Neutral with the Satisfaction on the Introduction and Orientation Program.
- Majority of 54.5 % of the Respondents are Agree with the Effectiveness of the Interviewing process.
- Majority of 40.9 % of the Respondents are Neutral with the Organizations Adequate Pool of Quality Applicants.
- Majority of 59.1 % of the Respondents are Agree with the Rating of Department Performances.

- Majority of 40.9 % of the Respondents are Agree with the Organizations Explanation about the job roles.
- Majority of 43.6 % of the Respondents are Strongly Agree with the Comfortable with the Interviewer While Interviewed.
- Majority of 43.6 % of the Respondents are Agree with the Internal Hiring Motivates them in the Organization.

Suggestions:

- Majority of the employees are satisfied with the HR Policy and Recruitment process.
- The company also provided the soft skills and job training to their employees, which is mandatory within organization.
- The organization should not majorly Clear job description is given to the candidates at the time of interview itself, to avoid disappointment after joining.
- The candidate should be informed in time whether they have been selected or not. There should not be any delay in informing the candidate
- Recruitment feedback should be taken by the candidates to improve the recruitment process.
- The employees should be called for the interview only after checking their educational qualifications and job experience in a proper way so as to save the time and cost involved in the recruitment process
- Depend on the application bank as the major source for the details of the candidate for recruitment purpose. It should also consider other sources which could provide them better options.
- Follow up to be done to the newly engaged employees to ensure that they have settled in and to check on how well they are doing. If they have any problems it is better to identify them at an early stage rather than allowing them to fester.

Conclusion:

An effective HR Policy and recruitment process reduces turnover, the HR Policy and recruitment process is the time we not only identify a candidate who has the experience and aptitude to do the job that the organization are looking to fill, but also to find someone who shares and endorses company's core values. The candidate will need to fit in well within the company's culture. The HR Policy and recruitment process should provide our company with an employee who adapts and works well with others in company's business. The project study entitled "HR Policy and recruitment process" has been carried out with special reference to Top QnQ Healthcare, Chennai the sample questionnaire was distributed to the employees indicate the positive result. However, the maximum employees are satisfied with the HR Policy and recruitment process. As satisfied and motivated employees helps organization to higher level of inputs.

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